

Provincial Clothing In The Book Al-Maqdisi, The Best Of Al-Taqasem

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 12, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 01, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Provincial Clothing , Al-Maqdisi Book , Al- Taqasem</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4487357</p>	<p><i>The human race throughout time still declares its need for clothing. Being a need to protect from the fluctuations of nature in the heat and cold, and to cover his nakedness. It is no secret to anyone the simplicity of human clothes in the beginning, and then man became elevated, so his need for clothes differed in their quality and shapes. And human beings gradually used clothing, starting with animal skins and dressing them as clothes for them. Then civilization and the civil development of man imposed, and the textile industry developed, He weaved what he needed of clothing, in a variety and different way, until it became a dress, not only as a need to prevent the vagaries of nature, but that the clothes were taken to show adornment and make-up and gain the respect of others, rather the clothes were taken to show the position of the one who wears them, as we will see in this study. It must be mentioned that our historian Al-Maqdisi, may God have mercy on him, like other historians and Arab travelers, does not detail an accurate description of the types of clothing, In order to be able to form clear images of it when writing about it, especially since many of these clothes are no longer used in the modern era.</i></p>

Introduction

He is Shams al-Din Abu Abdullah Muhammad bin Ahmad Al-Maqdisi, he was born in Jerusalem in Palestine. About the year 335 AH / 946 AD, and he died in the year 375 AH / 982 AD. An updated writer denies that this is the year of his death, and says: "And many researchers were mistaken when they made that year the year of his death, which is likely to be the year 385 AH / 995 AD or later"⁽ⁱ⁾.

Al-Maqdisi is considered one of the travelers referred to by Lebanon, as he is a traveler who suffered what he suffered from the trouble of traveling, He toured most Islamic cities and spent many years of his life wandering around the Islamic world, gathering information for his book (The best division in knowing the regions), through observation and investigation, He visited Iraq, Egypt, Arabia, Persia, and the countries of the Maghreb, with the exception of India and Andalusia.

It was praised by orientalist, as SPRENGER considered it: The largest geographer known to all mankind, As KRAMERAS put it: The most original Arab geographer, While ADAM METZ considered it his book, the culmination of the progress made in Arab geography books in describing countries⁽ⁱⁱ⁾. Metz states that Al-Maqdisi: He traveled until the kingdoms were dazed, carried by the current travels, and he was attracted by the travel and tourism life. Al-Maqdisi says about himself: There was nothing left of what befell travelers, except that he took a share from him, other than kiddy and riding big ones, and that he spent more than ten thousand dirhams on his travels⁽ⁱⁱⁱ⁾.

His book (The Best of Al-Taqasim), Al-Maqdisi did not appear until he reached the age of forty. As for his experiences, he says about them: She pondered, disciplined, and became devoted to worship. I sermoned on the pulpits, and the call to prayer was raised on the minarets, and I was in front of the worshipers in the mosques. And I ate "puree" with mystics, and "Bread and broth" with the Khanqaaan. It dealt with food "Porridge" with Nawati. And wandered into the wilds And I kept the road in the deserts, And I believed in piety for a long time, And I ate the forbidden at times, And I owned slaves, and I carried ginger on my head, And oversaw repeatedly drowning, and cut roads on our convoys. I was imprisoned and accused of espionage, and I walked under the sky and snow, And the era of kings descended between the future, And I dwelt among the fools in the weaving district, How much you have achieved glory and honor, And my assassination was plotted more than once, And I wore the clothes left to kings, And they commanded me to pray, Many times I was stripped and poor^(iv).

Al-Maqdisi divided the regions into fourteen regions, and when he mentioned the East, he meant the state of the Saman family, as for the East: it means Persia, Kerman and Sindh. As for the Arab regions he mentioned, and Al-Maqdisi passed by, they are: Arabia, Iraq, Aqor, Levant, Egypt and Morocco. He mentioned the regions of the Ajam, which are: the Levant, the Daylam^(v), Rehab, the mountains, Khuzestan, Fars, Kerman, and Sindh.

We will mention the clothes that Al-Maqdisi mentioned according to the sequence of pages in the book, so that he can discover the clothes of each city or region he mentioned and he passed by.

Shiraz^(vi): About their clothes, Al-Maqdisi says: Those who wear Tailsan do not obtain the ability and respect because there Tailsan,^(vii) to dress everyone wear: The honest, the lowly, the scientist and the ignorant. So everyone wears it, Sometimes the "Tailsan" does not respect, because some drunks have scattered Tailsan which they wear and dragged her to the ground. Al-Maqdisi adds about the importance of wearing the costume, saying: I was not allowed to see the minister, and I was withheld from that, but when I came wearing a (armor)^(viii) Permission for me to enter^(ix).

Sana'a^(x): For the temperate weather in the city of Sana'a, and the approaching temperatures on all days of the year, The weather was similar in those days, so the people of Sanaa "dress in the winter and the summer is one"^(xi). As long as we are in Yemen, most of their clothes are cotton, and they always wear slippers,^(xii) That is, they wear slippers, and al-Maqdisi did not tell us what kind of slippers they are wearing.

Mecca: described by Al-Maqdisi (a city of Territory), He says: They wear apron^(xiii), a shirtless apron only a few^(xiv).

Makha: Makha is one of the cities of Taiz in Yemen, located on the coast of the Red Sea "And in the city of Mocha they reproach those who wear the apron, It is only one apron wrapped in."^(xv)

Iraq: On the clothes of preachers in Iraq, it is seen that they wear cellars^(xvi) and regions^(xvii). On the people of Iraq as well, he says: "Habits of dressing, cosmetics and Tailsan, Wrapping turbans and wearing sock^(xviii), What is less compared Tailsan^(xix). As we see, they were taking care of appearance and choose beautiful clothes, And they did not leave to wear slippers, As well as wearing a sock permanently. And in the garment they make a round rag, which means that the people of Iraq were wearing Tailsan without make it rotated.

Wasit^(xx): And from its cities (Al-Nu'maniyah), in which it is manufactured "Fine Hazel woolen clothes and clothes"^(xxi), It seems that Wasit's clothes liked Al-Maqdisi, so she made it with Fine Hazel.

City of Peace: As for Baghdad, the capital of the Islamic caliphate, on the day Al-Maqdisi visited it, he said: "And in Baghdad aprons and a fine Yakankee^(xxii) turban^(xxiii)". Seen in Baghdad "Antics, and the colors of silk clothes, and more^(xxiv), and silk clothing, as it is known, means the clothes woven by the silkworm, It is silk, which indicates the luxury and good standard of living enjoyed by the people of Baghdad at the time.

Basra: Also, Basra, like Baghdad, in a life of luxury that Al-Maqdisi saw through their wearing of silk and the wool they weave with, Or what weaves with Ebrism: The best silk, He says: "From them carry dates to the edges, and henna, and they have prickly and violets and (Maord) "^(xxv) "it seems that violets here were received, as a plant with a good smell, perhaps to extract perfumes from it, and (Maord) here I think rose water used as flavorings for food.

Al-Abla^(xxvi): Thin linen garments are made^(xxvii).

As for **Kufa^(xxviii)**: Turban made of Al-Kaz "It is the fabric that is filled with pure silk and other than its weft" and violets^(xxix).

Mosul: Shams Al-Din al-Maqdisi says: from "I extend^(xxx) the Roman garments of wool and linen on the work of the Sicilians"^(xxxi), Linen seems to have different types, Including Rumia, which is made by craftsmen from Sicily, an island in the Mediterranean, belonging to Italy.

Constantinople^(xxxii): And there is the (royal^(xxxiii)) (brocade^(xxxiv)) factory

Lattakia^(xxxv): Al-Maqdisi says: "Then we came to Lattakia, and then we ended up at the opening of the cave, which is the hollow of a mountain..If there are thirteen men lying in it, each of them will have a robe,I don't know it's made of wool or lint; Except it is dirty, Dusty cladding cracks Just as Atqaka slave, His clothing covered his face and the rest of his body.. And on some of them pumice to the half of their legs, and some with soles and some with sandals^(xxxvi)..They wipe them, shake off the dust of their clothes, and straighten their clothes on them.. And they trim their nails.. Mujahid said.. So he thinks that they are the owners of the cave, and God knows best^(xxxvii).

The story of seeing those in the cave dates back to the year 102 AH / 720 AD, when some Muslims went on a mission to Constantinople, and from there they returned to Lattakia, then they stood on this cave in which they saw those sleeping. and the story looks like science fiction, especially when reading "They trim their nails", These nails do not grow until they are in the body of the living, But the story accurately depicts these (Cavemen) clothes for us, He mentions the robe, clothing, slippers and slippers, which is a depiction of the people's clothes at that time.

Jerusalem: Of its people, he says, "Most of them weave the mats and twist the ropes^(xxxviii), and the word "weave" indicates their knowledge of weaving,they must know the fabric of their clothes as well.

Adraa: In Palestine, which is an "extremist Hijazi Levantine city, they have the mantle^(xxxix) of the Messenger of God (May God bless him and grant him peace) and his covenant, which is written in Adeem"^(xl). and we are still in Jerusalem, in which the "clothes enlightening^(xli) and Balaisi and ropes^(xlii)". And it seems that (Al-Balaisiya) is a type of clothing, but I did not find it in the dictionaries of Arab clothes.

Al-Maqdisi tells us about Aleppo in the Levant, from which he brings "cotton and clothes"^(xliii). It is no secret that the best clothes are made from cotton, which is available in Aleppo. And from Damascus Al-Maasour, Al-Balaisi and Dibaj^(xliv).

Al-Maqdisi tells us about leather tanners in the Levant, and says: "the most of the tanners in this region are Jews"^(xlv), and it seems that they have a monopoly on this profession and that they are good at it. And we stay in the Levant, and he says about its people that ""They have beautifully dressed robes"^(xlv), every scientist and ignorant, And they do not loosen up in the summer, rather they are the slippers of Al-Taq"^(xlvii), and they reveal the rain"^(xlviii), and no Digging in a circular motion Tailsan"^(*)."

The dress of the two villages, Prestaq Elijah^(†) and Nablus was just one garment, without trousers^(‡). Al-Maqdisi specifies the (the villagers) garment, only one garment, Without wearing underpants (Long men's panty).

Al-Maqdisi teaches us about the benefit of the location of the island of Cyprus near the coasts of the Levant, and how goods are carried from it to Muslims and Arabs in general, he says: "In front of Tire, the island of Cyprus is located..And Muslims have compassion and capacity for the abundance of good things and clothes they carry"^(§).

The Sufis, who he met in the Levant, Our Sheikh Al-Maqdisi tells us about their gathering with their professor, and says: "and Mount Golan ... and with it I found Abu Ishaq al-Ballouti among forty men who wore wool"^(**), He did not detail what their woolen clothes were like ⁽⁵⁴⁾.

Africa ⁽⁵⁵⁾: The Umayyads, to the blackness, says: "The same as the residence by two, which was returned to one by the Umayyads, and the like for wearing white, which the Banu Abbas returned to blackness"⁽⁵⁶⁾.

We remain in Africa, and in Morocco in particular, for they "enter the bathroom without mausers ⁽⁵⁷⁾ except for a few, and they look the least. Al-Rasatiq with clothes and al-Suqa with tissues ⁽⁶⁰⁾.

Morocco: He says, and from Morocco carries commercial goods and there are various garments from the cities of Morocco. "And it has merchants that carry from gently ⁽⁶¹⁾ clothes of wool and garments, from Sicilya ⁽⁶²⁾, good short clothes"⁽⁶³⁾. About Morocco also, al-Maqdisi speaks, and mentions an animal that comes out of its skin with soft ground, from which they make clothes of various colors in one day, and these clothes are very expensive, and it is forbidden to export or carry them outside the country.

He says: "The wonders in this region are many, including Abu Qalamoun, which is a bear rubbing against stones on the coast of the sea, and it falls and its righteousness while it is in the lane of Khazar ⁽⁶⁴⁾. Its color is the color of gold. He carried that to countries, except for what was hidden from them. Perhaps the garment reached ten thousand dinars."⁽⁶⁵⁾

Sudan: He says about Sudan "and the Nuba and Habash (their dealings) with clothes"⁽⁶⁶⁾ and perhaps al-Maqdisi means that their commercial dealings are by barter for clothes, and not for cash.

The Arabian Peninsula: He says on the authority of the people of the island that "their fiancé is a grocer and their ruler is shovels with great fanaticism, and they wear Davidic shields in sedition"⁽⁶⁷⁾. Al-Maqdisi said that it was astonishing to find a people's preacher who works as a grocer, or that their ruler works in the manufacture of slippers. I believe that it is a sign of simplicity, asceticism and integrity, despite what he describes as fanaticism and wearing armor when disputes and strife. And he remains in the Arabian Peninsula, and he reminds us of some of their worn out and shabby clothes, as he says, "Until I reached the head of the corner, I paid what was on me of clothes to some of the floats and took from them armored hair, fine sandals and a shabby handkerchief"⁽⁶⁸⁾.

Numujt: a city from the Levant region, which is the Kasbah of Bukhara. Al-Maqdisi saw in it the luxury that people live there, and "Hashm grew up, wearing silk and brocade, and drank in pots of gold and silver"⁽⁶⁹⁾.

Darzangi: It is also one of the cities of the East. Al-Maqdisi portrays to us that its people, their common folk, work with wool and make garments of garments, and he says: "Most of its people are wooleners who work garments"⁽⁷⁰⁾.

Iranshahr: We are still in the cities of the East, and this city produces bright garments for the beholder, and it was acquired by the people of Iraq as a metropolis of the Abbasid Caliphate and the people of Egypt, and we read about this country:

And from Koyan, as one of the cities of the Islamic East as well, clothes were raised from it ⁽⁷²⁾. But Al-Maqdisi did not specify the type and shape of these clothes. Likewise, the city of Istowa was a source for the export of many garments, according to the author of Ahsan al-Taqasim ⁽⁷³⁾, and he says on the authority of Hittal, in which people are called white clothes ⁽⁷⁴⁾.

Nishapur ⁽⁷⁵⁾: He pays close attention to the types of garments that he saw in this city, and their number, and says: "From them the garments of the Hafziyyah and the bibs, the chaotic turbans, the Hafiz, the ragtag, the

ritual, and the veils, and between the dresses and the epics with the dwarf, the silent, the tabby, the Saidi, the sardar, the al-mashtiyab, the al-marsh,⁽⁷⁶⁾

I did not stand on some of these garments, but Al-Rakhtaj and Al-Takhtaj: a type of silk or linen made in Nishapur⁽⁷⁷⁾. And melhem: it is derived from the word (weft) or (weft) which is a fabric in which the warp is made of silk and the weft is made of cotton, linen or wool⁽⁷⁸⁾. As for the solid: it is the garment that does not mix with color, or it is the uniform that is all-embroidered (silk) that is not mixed with cotton or anything else, and it is a thin fabric⁽⁷⁹⁾. Al-Atabi: According to the locality of Al-Attabia, on the western side of Baghdad, it is located at the edge of the desert, and was famous for its textile industry⁽⁸⁰⁾. As for the solution: Hilla: two garments, buttons and robe, and it is called Hilla because it is not permissible for the wearer as it is permissible for a man on the ground⁽⁸¹⁾.

Nasa⁽⁸²⁾ and Abuward⁽⁸³⁾: Among these cities are silk and the clothes that are made of it, "the silk and its garments ... and the foxes and linens are spoiled"⁽⁸⁴⁾.

Tous⁽⁸⁵⁾: He says, among them are the high and strict⁽⁸⁶⁾ brams, and among them are the good tacks, the good fridges, and the takah.

He returns to Nishapur, and says of her female friends, "Many thick clothes"⁽⁸⁷⁾.

Herat⁽⁸⁸⁾: Including a lot of clothing, Dipaj Don and Khaldi⁽⁸⁹⁾.

Mero⁽⁹⁰⁾: He says, including "the epics and the maks of the silk⁽⁹¹⁾, the alabrism and the cotton"⁽⁹²⁾.

Quhistan⁽⁹³⁾: It contains clothes and clothes that "resemble Nisaburiyya with eggs, rugs and good prayer rooms."

Gharj al-Shar⁽⁹²⁾: Including "gold and fiber⁽⁹³⁾ and fine rugs and bags"⁽⁹⁴⁾

Bukhara⁽⁹⁵⁾: Al-Maqdisi provides us with important and abundant information about this town, and the various types of clothing it contains, and says, including "soft clothes, prayer halls, rugs, hotel clothes, zero pulpits, al-Tabari and horse-bundles woven into prison and Ashmonite clothes"⁽⁹⁶⁾. And the soft clothes seem to be the thin clothes, which were used as underwear, and Al-Maqdisi stops us on an important information, which is the presence of hotels, he said: (Hotel clothes), and it seems that it was widespread and known at the time. The inmates (people of imprisonment) worked and produced all kinds of materials and tools that were woven in the prisons.

Dabbousia and Zhar: It is one of the cities of Khurasan, and it is attributed to it "the garments of the wathari, which are clothes of the color of the solid, and I heard some of the sultans in Baghdad call it the dybaj of Khurasan"⁽⁹⁷⁾.

Rabanjin: It is also one of the cities of Khorasan, and it is attributed to it "red pulp and prayer halls"⁽⁹⁸⁾, and as we mentioned, the pulp is everything that wears it for rain.

Bulgar: We are still in the Khorasan region, and al-Maqdisi talks to us about her clothes and what is produced in that region, including "cold, furs, quilting clothes, dykesh, and melhem masks..and Aring clothes"⁽⁹⁹⁾. It seems that the quilting used to produce its own cloth. As for the "Bishkesh" brocade, it may be attributed to the city of its production, as well as Arbakh's clothes.

Samarkand⁽¹⁰⁰⁾: It is famous for Simkon and Samarkand clothes .. also a brocade that carries to the Turk and red clothes called Mamargel and Senizi, and many jeans and his clothes⁽¹⁰¹⁾ Simkon's clothes, perhaps like Samarkand, are attributed to the city of their production.

From Punaketh, he produced "Turkistan clothing"⁽¹⁰²⁾, and Banakath from the cities of Turkestan.

Al-Shash⁽¹⁰³⁾: Including the chapels and bannets⁽¹⁰⁴⁾ .. and the cotton is carried to the Turk⁽¹⁰⁵⁾

From Ferghana⁽¹⁰⁶⁾, she produced "white clothes"⁽¹⁰⁷⁾

And from Beyond the River, he says: Their fiancé did not wear robes⁽¹⁰⁸⁾, but rather a shield, and their people wore slippers⁽¹⁰⁹⁾ in winter and summer, and they wear less. The tax on passenger cloth is Dirham⁽¹¹⁰⁾.

Al-Maqdisi returns again to the city of Nishapur, and tells us that "the jurists and the elders, and they turn around only those who despise and have clothes that they are unique to in winter. The group of Battus, Abiord and Herat do this, and the people of Sijistan⁽¹¹¹⁾ round turbans like crowns, and they do not flatten with what is beyond the river except for large ones.

The region of Daylam⁽¹¹²⁾: Al-Maqdisi praises this region because it is "the region of silk and wool, with its clever craftsmen"⁽¹¹³⁾, as well as the people of Estrabad, because "their commoners are the weavers of the silk." Because "Hassan has wonderful clothes"⁽¹¹⁴⁾. And he talks about the city of Saria, and he says it is "full of sciences and luxurious clothes"⁽¹¹⁵⁾.

Qums⁽¹¹⁶⁾: He says on the authority of its people, "They have white handkerchiefs made of teacher cotton, young and old, stools, and a stuffing, and the handkerchief of them may reach two thousand dirhams. And they have clothes, plaits, and thin woolen clothes."⁽¹¹⁷⁾ And the handkerchiefs contained a belt to tighten their circles, and it was probably made of silk, cotton, or wool⁽¹¹⁸⁾. And it was (Suwajih), that is, what is not engraved in it, is stuffed, because it is the white garment that they use as an apron, and it was of the expensive and valuable type because its price might be (two thousand dirhams). He speaks about gentle clothes, which are thin underwear⁽¹¹⁹⁾.

And from Jarjan ⁽¹²⁰⁾, also from Daylam region, he says: "They have the scarfs, which are carried to Yemen ... and they have a brochure" ⁽¹²¹⁾. As we can see, these masks that women used to use for the head and face together are made of silk. And we stay there in the region of Daylam, and from Tabaristan ⁽¹²²⁾: "Including the garments that are preferred over the Persian and Tiala and the Hanish clothes are carried to the horizons, and many things are sold in Makkah." ⁽¹²³⁾ And the garment of the henish, is a type of plain cloth, and it is usually used for tasks that require endurance and durability, such as making tents, sails and bags, and it is also used by painters as a surface for drawing paintings, and henish is usually made from hemp ⁽¹²⁴⁾.

Al-Maqdisi tells us: The people of Gorgan, who ordained them, "do not exaggerate touching" ⁽¹²⁵⁾, and about the council, then he says: "And if they had a funeral, they uncovered their heads, and gathered together, and the mourner and the comforter were wrapped in the garments, and turned them on their heads and beards, and they had councils ... with their hands the zubinat and they had the Tabariyya axes" ⁽¹²⁶⁾. And from Gorgan also, which is one of its cities (Pierre), he talks about her women, and says: "And you do not see a woman during the day, but they go out at night in a black cloth" ⁽¹²⁷⁾.

And from the Rehab region, "the wearable fleeces rise and the miraculous dislocation" ⁽¹²⁸⁾. It is no secret that the disconnect is the strap of the pants ⁽¹²⁹⁾, so why did he say the strange thing about it? Maybe because the quality is good and the colors are multiple. Al-Maqdisi enumerates for us the types of clothes that are produced in this region, such as a lot of abram, linen clothes, wool clothes, rugs, pillows, patterns, thin tacks, and al-sour, and then says that Monday of the week was devoted to the sale of abram and clothes ⁽¹³⁰⁾.

Al-Maqdisi notes, the companions of the Sultan in the city of Tabriz are sealed with gold ⁽¹³¹⁾, as part of the ornament for men. And he provides us with a number of different kinds of clothes from several cities, such as loose-fitting, cotton linen, combs, thongs and socks, pumice, and thin and fine garments ⁽¹³²⁾. And he saw in the city of Isfahan ⁽¹³³⁾, their turbans like a mud with the creation of a monster ⁽¹³⁵⁾. In Khuzestan Province ⁽¹³⁴⁾, we see "brocade and prickly uniforms, and sprouts from cotton and silk ... and like licorice pricks do not see" ⁽¹³⁶⁾, that is, their clothes are of original silk or woven from silk and wool, and they praise the licorice ⁽¹³⁷⁾, and likewise, the The licorice women weaved patterns and spun wool ⁽¹³⁸⁾ to make clothes from it.

Covert ⁽¹³⁹⁾: Al-Maqdisi says: It is the home of skilled craftsmen of genuine silk fabric and cotton clothes, and it has markets for selling fabrics, and that it is: "The metal of every skilled in brocade and cotton work ... and the mosque is in the middle of the markets in bazaars. .

Ahwaz ⁽¹⁴⁰⁾: And with clothes that are woven of wool, alabrum and silk, and it seems from al-Maqdisi's words that clothes are cheaply priced within the reach of the poor.

Ram Hormuz ⁽¹⁴²⁾: It seems that the city has many merchants of fabrics and other materials, even the fabric market has various kinds of clothes. And he refers to their use of (kilo) on summer nights in order to avoid bugs ⁽¹⁴³⁾, and as it is known that (kilo) is of a very thin type of fabric, and has pores to enter air to breathe, and it prevents bugs from entering through it.

He returns to the city of Al-Sous, and says I entered it and went to the mosque, "and on me a cypress ⁽¹⁴⁴⁾ wool cypress and an optical towel ⁽¹⁴⁵⁾ .. And I carried the clothes to me .. and their drawings do not require anything but just plain clothes.

Shiraz: Al-Maqdisi enumerates the clothes that people wear in it, and in other cities close to it. He states, on the authority of Shiraz, that "preachers in it wear basements and regions on the drawing of Iraq ... and enter the bathroom without mias ... From the licorice, the linen and the prickles ... and from the military, the silk masks are carried to Baghdad, and good clothes that remain, and hemp clothes and handkerchiefs" ⁽¹⁴⁶⁾.

And we remain in the Ahwaz, about which Al-Maqdisi says that it includes "fine silk towels that women wear" ⁽¹⁴⁷⁾.

And from the province of Fars ⁽¹⁴⁸⁾, in which he makes fridges, ceramics, fine rugs, linen garments that resemble reeds, brocades and various types of jumpsuits. ⁽¹⁴⁹⁾ As we can see, this region has one of the many industries for the clothes that were worn by the people of that region, and the regions that export to her .

Al-Maqdisi tells us that in the city of Arajan ⁽¹⁵⁰⁾ a market for clothes has doors that are closed every night ⁽¹⁵¹⁾, as well as the city of (Soro) from the same region, which has a market for clothes, as if he had betrayed him ⁽¹⁵²⁾. And he returns to Shiraz from Fars province, and he sees men in it "entering the baths without mias ... and you do not see the owner of the pallisan an amount, and I saw the people of the pilgrim who are drunk, and the battered and the Christians wear him" ⁽¹⁵³⁾. It seems that the talisman was not worn in other provinces, unless it was of a significant social status and special, with the exception of the city of Shiraz. And Shiraz was famous for its cladding and coldness, as Al-Maqdisi says ⁽¹⁵⁴⁾. And from the cities of Fars Province (Kord Fna Khusraw), to which the souafin and brocade makers were transported ⁽¹⁵⁵⁾.

Toz ⁽¹⁵⁶⁾: which he praises, and says about her, that there is "for the clothes that you work with from linen, do you not see it called a dressing, and most of it works with Kazron, and these are the best and the best work" ⁽¹⁵⁷⁾.

Conclusion:

Fars Province: Al-Maqdisi says about him: "The commoners wear black clothes, uncover wool, and multiply . This research is about the social life of Arabs, Muslims in general, and all people, and this is what made me write about this topic (regional clothing) of the peoples he visited and where was the historian Muslim traveler

(Shams). Al-Din Muhammad bin Ahmed Al-Maqdisi) who died in the fourth century AH during the period of the Abbasid Caliphate.

And it sheds light on an important aspect of the conditions of people of all levels.

Since people are the same people in different eras, there are no differences in the tools used, the clothes they decorate, the quality of food, and other traditions that highlight a time span of millions of years.

The types of clothing and the occasions in which this or that clothes are worn are covered in this study, which was taken as an indicator of the position of the person who sometimes wears it, and here we can stand on the opinions of what we have. The historian al-Maqdisi saw.

References:

Al-Wazar: All that is covered, and it is the Urdu, one of which is an applique, and it is the buttons that used to be used by men during the era of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH). The bazar is a piece of fabric that Arab women are wrapped in. Dozy, A Dictionary of Clothes, pp. 31-32.

Al-Maqdisi, Hasan, p. 99.

Al-Maqdisi: Ihsan al-Taqasim, pp. 99-100.

The cellar: men's outerwear, of Persian origin, that is folded under the armpit in a diagonal fashion, and was closed at the front with buttons, and was completely hemmed in the position of the rank. It is a jacket usually made of very soft cotton tulle, colored in red, yellow, green or another color. Dozy, Lexicon, pp. 284-291.

The regions: They are the belts, which are of gold or silver, and we have never read about a logic or an area of leather or cloth. Dozy, Lexicon, p. 340.

Al-Shroub: What is thinned out of linen. Al-Obeidi, Salah Hussein, Arab-Islamic Clothes in the Second Abbasid Era, Dar Al-Rasheed for Publishing, (Baghdad, 1980), Ministry of Culture and Information Publications, p. 69.

Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 129.

Wasit: It was named "Buss" because it mediated between Basra and Kufa. It was built in the year 68 AH. Ibn al-Faqih, Abu Abdullah Ahmad al-Hamdhani, (d. Around 340 AH / 951 CE), Al-Balad, edited by Yusef Al-Hadi, The World of Books, Edition 2, (Beirut, 2009), pp. 260-269.

Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, pp. 128-129.

Yankaneki turbans: the turban is: the kulota or kulutat, from the piece of cloth wrapped around it. The turban is usually white, and of separate colors. It is made of black silk inlaid with gold or cashmere, or from red or white wool. In Andalusia, it is not worn except in rare cases. And I did not see the word yankee in the clothing dictionaries. Dozy, Lexicon, pp. 250-254.

Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, pp. 128-129.

Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 128.

Al-Maqdisi, the same source.

Al-Abla: A city in Iraq between it and Basra, four leagues, and it is small in size, has a good house, wide architecture, full of people, and they are fertile and prosperous. Utbah bin Ghazwan conquered it at the time of Caliph Omar bin Abi Al-Khattab (may God bless him). Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd Al-Moattar, pp. 8-9.

Al-Maqdisi, the same source.

Kufa: the largest city in Iraq, the greatest Egypt and the Dome of Islam, and it was the first city that Muslims had envisioned in Iraq in the year 14 AH / 635 AD. And from Baghdad to Kufa thirty leagues. It has many lands, farms and palm trees, and its people are flowing, and its water is fresh, and on six miles from Kufa a great dome with high corners, in it is the tomb of Imam Ali bin Abi Talib (peace be upon him). In an illiterate state, a hidden one does not care. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, p. 501.

Al-Maqdisi, the same source.

Amad: a city from the core of the island from the works of Mosul, and the island between the Tigris and Mosul, and it is a large city fortified on a mountain, and some scholars are attributed to it. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd Al-Moattar, pp. 3-4.

Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 145.

Constantinople: Rome was in the old days the house of the Roman Kingdom. 29 Kings descended it from their kings. Then Constantine the Great reigned in it, then moved to Byzantium and built a wall over it and called it Constantinople, which is now called Istanbul, after the Muslim leader Muhammad the Conqueror conquered it in 1453 AD. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd Al-Moattar, pp. 481-482.

Brocade: It is embossing and embellishment, and it was said that it is the style, and it was said that it is a thin, well-colored garment. And brocade is a kind of green clothes. In the description of alabaster silk, there is coarse brocade, and what is thin of silk is brocade. And sondos are a thin cut of brocade. Al-Obeidi, Arab Clothes, p. 18.

Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 147.

- Lattakia: from the coastal Levant, and the sea from it to the west, and a role for the marble industry was established in Latakia. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd Al-Moattar, p. 507.
- Shamshekat: it means a shoe, a shoe, a boot, or a slipper. Dozy, Lexicon, p. 193.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, pp. 153-154.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 162.
- Barda: a longitudinal piece of thick woolen cloth, which people use to cover their bodies with it during the day and also wear a cover during the night. As for the color of this cloth, it was brown, or gray, and it seems that in ancient times this fabric was always striped, and the apostle's cold was a thick Najrani hail on the border. Dozy, Lexicon, pp. 55-56.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 178.
- Munayriah: The adjective Munir, whose feminine is Munayyah, means what it means to be thick, when speaking of skin, and Munayriah refers to a type of thick clothing. Dozy, Lexicon, p. 345.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 180.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 181.
- Al-Maqdisi, the same source.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 183.
- Urdu: a type of. Al-Taq slippers: the word insole means sandals, made of rough camel skins, and they connect it to two traps, one of which passes on the center of the foot, and the other is between the thumb and forefinger of the foot, and the most luxurious slippers are those from Yemen. Dozy, Lexicon, pp. 340-341.
- Al-Matarah: As indicated by the origin of the word, what is meant is a garment that the deceased wears from the rain, which is made of wool. Dozy, Lexicon, p. 329.
- Al-Maqdisi, the same source.
- Elia: A city in the Levant, which is Jerusalem, and it is a venerable ancient city on a mountain. It includes the Church of the Holy Sepulcher, and it is the pilgrimage church to which from all the countries of Rome, and they said it is one of the wonders of the world and it includes the Al-Aqsa Mosque. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd Al-Moattar, p. 68.
- Al-Maqdisi, the same source.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 184.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 188.
- Tennis: from the cities of Egypt, a large city in which there are many traces of the former, and its people are left-wing and wealthy, and the most of them are woven. . Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd Al-Moattar, p. 137.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 201.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p.202.
- Bahnasa: Al-Hamiri calls it (Bahnasy), a city in Upper Egypt, and it is full of people, a university for various nations, and by which it works the Bahnese drapes and weaves styles, sultans, large rackets, and archaic clothes. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd Al-Moattar, p. 114.
- Al-Maqdisi, Hassan, p.202.
- Al-Maqdisi, Hassan, p. 203.
- Al-Maqdisi, the same source.
- Al-Maqdisi, Hassan, p. 205.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p.208.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 213.
- Al-Razi, Muhammad bin Abi Bakr Abd al-Qadir (d.666 AH / 1268 CE), Mukhtar al-Sahah, Dar al-Kitab al-Arabiyya, (Beirut, 1981), p. 338.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 213.
- Africa: a great and great work in the western lands of Egypt, and a people said: the meaning of Africa: the owner of the sky and its length from Cyrenaica in the east to Tangiers in the west. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, p. 47.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 238.
- Al-Miyazar: men's underwear, meaning the piece of cloth that covers the awrah and that is worn from the navel to the bottom. It has been used in several cases, including the bathrooms to cover the awrah. Al-Obeidi, Arab Clothes, pp. 181-182.
- The cowl: the cowl: a common headwear for men and women. The hood was worn by a headscarf, either alone or with turbans wrapped around it. Al-Obeidi, Arab Clothes, p. 136.
- The Pyrenees: It is an outer garment, and it is every garment whose head is attached to it, whether it is a shield, rain, or a jubah. The prince was one of the clothes of the Jews. According to Metz, in the second century AH, Christians used to wear bathing suits as well. Metz, Islamic Civilization, Part 1, p. 80.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 239.

- Cyrenaica: a large ancient city between Alexandria and Ifriqiya, and it has many traces of the former, and from the redness of its soil the clothes of its inhabitants and those who dispose of it reddish, Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, p.91.
- Sicily: A silky island in a piece of the Levantine sea, which was conquered by Muslims in early Islam, and Sicily was the name of one of its cities, so the whole island was attributed to it, and it contains many cities, and it was opened in the year twelve and two hundred. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, pp. 366-367.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 239.
- Al-Khaz: one (khuzouz) of clothing, which is woven from silk or from wool and silk. Al-Razi, Mukhtar As-Sahih, p. 174.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, pp. 240-241.
- Al-Maqdisi, Hassan, p. 242.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 253.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ahsan al-Taqasim, p. 256.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 281.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 283.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 315.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 318.
- Al-Maqdisi, pp. 318-319
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 323.
- Nishapur: so named because Sabor passed by, and it is from the country of Khorasan, which is a vast country. And from Nishapur, a group of Akbar al-Fadhla, a beautiful city, and its buildings of clay. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, p. 588.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, pp. 323-324.
- Al-Tha'alabi, Abu Mansour Abdul-Malik bin Muhammad bin Ismail (d. 429 AH / 1037 AD), by Latif al-Maarif, (Braille reprint, 1867 CE), p. 194.
- Al-Thaalabi, Latif, p. 201.
- Al-Thaalabi, Latif, p. 194.
- Al-Obaidi, The Arab Clothes, p. 54.
- Al-Obaidi, Arab Clothes, p. 132.
- Nasa: a city from Khor Nishapur, Al-Masoudi said: It is from the land of Persia, and it is a fortified city with many water and orchards, and it has wide ancestors. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, p. 579
- Abuward: from the cities of Khurasan, and from the people of Abiurd: Muhammad bin Ahmad Abu Al-Muzaffar Al-Abiordi. He has many classifications, including: the different and the mixed. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, p. 7.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 324.
- Tous: a city from Nishapur, and Tus al-Great is called Nuqan, and it is a large, well-built city, with many markets, including streets, full of places with clear directions, and has cities and pulpits. And in it, Imam Reza, peace be upon him, died and was buried there. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, pp. 398-399.
- The bram: the brim is a type of body tie, and it is like a twisted rope, having two colors. Dozy, Lexicon, p. 65.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, pp. 324, 235; Al-Obeidi, Arab Clothes, p. 193.
- Al-Maqdisi, the same source.
- Herat: a country in Khorasan. It is a bustling city with a surrounding area on its sides. Herat has four hundred villages, and Herat Al-Ahnaf bin Qais was inaugurated in the succession of Othman bin Affan (may God bless him), Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd Al-Maatar, pp. 594-595.
- Al-Maqdisi, the same source.
- Meru: from Khurasan, called Umm Khurasan, and Mero in Persian al-Marah, and the Shah of the King, and in it Yazdegerd, the last Persian king, was killed in the year thirty-one. It is known as the primary Shahjan architecture. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd Al-Moattar, pp. 532-533.
- Muqi'i: The mask or mask is among the covers that a woman has taken for both the head and face, and the mask is what she convinces with a garment that covers her head and her merits. Ibn Saydah, Ali bin Ismail (d. 458 AH / 1065 AD), Al-Mohassad, House of the Great Printing of the Emir, (Beirut, dt), vol 4, p. 38.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 324.
- Quhistan: from Kaur Nishapur. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd Al-Moattar, p. 485.
- Al-Maqdisi, the same source.
- Gharj Al-Shar: from the cities of Khorasan. Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 324.
- Felt: (Feed) with one skin weight (Felt) and (Felt). And (felting) what is worn from it to rain. Al-Razi, Mukhtar As-Sahih, p. 589.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 324.
- Bukhara: from the country of Khurasan, which is a vast country that heals large cities and beauties and many trees. . Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd Al-Moattar, pp. 82-83.

- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 324.
- Al-Maqdisi, the same source.
- Al-Maqdisi, the same source.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 325.
- Samarkand: A city from Khurasan, and it is said that it was built during the days of Alexander, and it is a great good city on the south of Wadi al-Sughd, the Qasaba of Sughd, Samarkand, and it has streets, buildings and palaces, hotels and baths. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, p. 322.
- Al-Maqdisi, the same source.
- Al-Maqdisi, the same source.
- Al-Shash: a great city from the work of Samarkand, and it has many cities. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, p. 335.
- Al-Aniqat: It refers to the piece of cloth that is placed in the sleeve of a shirt under the armpit location and is called a naffa or an armpit groove. Dozy, Lexicon, p. 79.
- Al-Maqdisi, the same source.
- Ferghana: In Khorasan, Anu Sherwan built it and transferred people to it from every house. Ferghana is the name of the region, and Ferghana is the gold and silver minerals. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, p. 440.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 325.
- Al-Qubba: a garment, outerwear for men, and it is of Persian origin. There are two types of vaults, in terms of their shape and appearance, namely the Arabic vault and the Persian vault. Al-Obeidi, Clothes, p. 280.
- Pumice: a type of slipper, made of leather, and men use it as well as women.
- Dozy, Lexicon, pp. 127-128.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, pp. 327, 340.
- Sijistan: a great country, comparable to Khurasan. They benefit from hedgehogs. And in the era of Sijistan, hedgehogs should not be killed in their country because their country is heavy with sand. Built by Zulkarnain, which is a lot of snakes and snakes. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, pp. 305-304.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 328.
- The province of Daylam: a city near the city of Salus, and Daylam are fortified in impregnable mountains, their tongue separate from the Persian, Rania and Armenian tongues. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd Al-Moattar, p. 255.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 353.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 358.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 359
- Al-Maqdisi, the same source.
- Qumus: A single work between Al-Rayy and Khurasan, a country of great destiny and vast, and its people are the Ajam people, and they are the most talented people to make thin, white woolen garments. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, p. 485.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 367.
- Dozy, The Lexicon, pp. 335-335.
- Al-Obaidi, Arab Clothes, p. 24.
- Gorgan: In Khorasan, the mountains and castles are predominant, and its forts may have reached 900. It is a very large city, and its construction with mud and its permanent rains, and its people are evidently chilling. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, pp. 160-161.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 367.
- Tabaristan: from the country of Khurasan, which is a great country with many forts and works impregnable to valleys, and its people are the nobles of the non-Arabs and the sons of their kings, and they are the best people and faces It is impregnable and fortified, and the Sea of Tabaristan is called the Khazar Sea. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, pp. 383-384.
- Al-Maqdisi, the same source.
- The information is taken from the internet (Google).
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 368.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 369.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 370.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 373.
- Dozy, The Dictionary, p.82.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 380.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 381.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, pp. 395-396.
- Isfahan: or Isfahan, which means the country of the Knights, and it is from the country of Fez, and they are two cities between them that are two miles apart. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, p. 43.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 399.

- Khuristan: in the land of Abadan, which is a large country, easy to water, and its country is full and the base of its Ahwaz country. And its people speak Persian and Arabic and another tongue they use among them. They are like the people of Iraq, and they wear shirts, thongs, and turbans. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, p. 225.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 402.
- Al-Sous: in the far reaches of the Maghreb, which is a venerable metropolis that combines all good and virtue, and its people are blends, and it is the land of drunkenness, and everything is made of it. All its greatness is made with it from ancient porcelain, and thin linens are made with it, and from clothes that no one can do. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, p. 330.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, pp. 407-408.
- Covert: A city in Ahwaz, Abu Musa al-Ash'ari conquered it, and it contains the tomb of Daniel. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, p. 140.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 409.
- Ahwaz: is Khuzestan and it is Ram Hormuz, and it is a place that collects seven khor.
- Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, pp. 61-62.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 410-411.
- Ram Hormuz: from the Al-Ahwaz region, near Wasit, Khuzestan, and it was opened by force in the last days of Abu Musa Al-Ash'ari. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, p. 266.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 413.
- The robe: a loose, wide robe that is wrapped around it, and the robe has two folds pressed on the wrists, but they are wide on the upper side, and it is open from the front and wide enough to be folded around the body. Dozy, Lexicon, pp. 97-98.
- A pad: a piece of inner body wear, and a pad is a type of short, thick clothes that is an apron, and one of it is a towel. Ibn Saydah, Al-Mohassan, vol. 4, p. 72.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, pp. 415-416.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 417.
- Al-Maqdisi, the same source.
- Fars Province: A well-known country, its origin in Persian, Pars Balba, which includes ten kor, including: Sabor, Atakhar, Azdashir, Arjan and others. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, p. 433.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 420.
- Arajan: A city between Persia and Ahwaz, and it contains the tomb of John the disciple, the companion of Jesus.
- Argan, O horses, it is my resolve that disperses the broken string
- Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd Al-Moattar, p. 25.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 425.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 428.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, 429, 440.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 430.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 431.
- Touwaz: It is in the books of Al-Baladanien (Tawaj), and it is a city in the land of Persia.
- Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd, p. 143.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 435.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 440.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 440.
- Dozy, The Dictionary, p. 193.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 441.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, pp. 442, 443.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan Al-Taqasim, p. 452.
- Bam: a city from the land of Kerman, a large city with markets, buildings, and many funds, and its people are wealthy merchants. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd Al-Moatar, p. 104.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, pp. 460, 465, 470.
- Makran: From the work of the bond, a plain land that is a mountain, its water and a shell, and its dates are small, and its good is little, and its evil is long. Al-Hamiri, Al-Rawd Al-Moattar, pp. 543-544.
- Earring: the earring that hangs on the lobe. Al-Razi, Mukhtar As-Sahih, p. 530.
- Al-Maqdisi, Ihsan al-Taqasim, p. 482.

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